

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DISO****FIRST NAME: HABIB ZANGINA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK.)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your seven key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Good Start to Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7-11)
2. The Usefulness of Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15-23)
3. Domination of the UK English by the US English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism - A Serious Offence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34-39)
5. Selecting the Rule of Style for the Essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40-42)

THE ACADEMIC WRITING BASICS, EUCLID UNIVERSITY FORMAT

1) INTRODUCTION

Having watched and read the assigned study material: Basic ACA-401 Tutorial and ACA-401 Course pack, I understand that they both teach the same learning points. The course pack gives additional explanations over the video on essay writing, ranging from topic selection to a list of references concisely and professionally (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-12).

The study material generally explains how to write a response paper using an RP template. It also displays how to personalise the RP template (name, course code, period and so on). The material guides students that 3-5 pages are enough for a response paper for a period. Regarding the rules of style, the material instructed students to use Turabian for a response paper, choose either the US or UK English (not combine the two at once), and make sure not to overuse punctuation unnecessarily, despite its significance in essay writing. Another important point the study material underscores is that students should

interact with the materials actively by making comments, expressing opinions, how practical it is and the difficulties faced in dealing with the material. It encourages students to use spelling checkers and Zotero for both in-text citations and a list of references. The material emphasises that students should not use footnotes for reference but clarification only in a response paper. Finally, it discourages plagiarism and hints at its consequence in academics (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 2-71).

2) GOOD START TO ESSAY WRITING

The first learning point that captured my attention when I started reading the period 1-course pack is the issue of how students can begin their essay writing. The material gives a critical point that hints that the steps for writing an essay are not rigidly linear (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021). However, the course pack never elaborates or sheds light on this issue which can help students understand this golden rule. The course pack should further give some examples to understand this issue better. Instead, it linearly illustrates the steps of essay writing in figure1(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8). The material should give two examples in that regard, one linear and the other non-linear, so that students can appreciate both and apply either of the two depending on which one works better for them.

'It is never advisable to procrastinate' (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). This learning point reflected my memory of undergraduate and master levels when procrastination caused some students to withdraw from their courses. My inner response to this learning point is to hasten my study and complete it within the shortest possible time. Another learning point I found to be a good reminder when selecting my essay writing topic is what I already know about the subject and not a mere interest in the topic (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8). Students often take topics and eventually change them due to their inadequate knowledge of the subject matter related to the topics.

One practical area the material covers, which I intend to apply when I begin researching my essay writing topic, includes taking important notes while reading, underlining and highlighting relevant information and paying attention to summaries. I will also jot down direct quotes, practical examples, case studies and significant statistics (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9). I now feel encouraged after studying the course pack to make a reading list before I embark on my essay writing. I also understand that EUCLID will accept any form of referencing in essay writing if it is strict in its format and consistent throughout the paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11).

3) THE USEFULNESS OF PUNCTUATION

I have discovered from the details given by the study material on punctuation that it will not only help me to write correctly but helps readers of my essay to understand my writing using short symbols that occupy few spaces. However, I found some difficulties in differentiating 'where' to use 'what' appropriately. For example, it has not yet been clear where to use angle and curly brackets, unlike round and square brackets which are clear to me (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021,17). During my secondary school days, when I learnt English, there was nothing like bullet points as part of punctuation marks. Today I use them

often in my job without knowing how to use them correctly until now after reading the period one-course pack. I appreciate this new learning!

I spent some time differentiating between the 12 usages of the comma (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 19-20). Some appeared to have very close similarities, and not easy to understand their difference. This situation made me concentrate and pay extra attention to grasp it correctly. I also felt that it was time to tighten my belt as this is period one, and six periods of similar work will follow.

4) DOMINATION OF THE UK ENGLISH BY THE US ENGLISH

Within the twinkle of an eye, I realised why US English had dominated UK English when I started reading chapter three of the course pack. The seven reasons in the chapter answered my long-unspoken inquiry on this issue. I still feel overwhelmed by the high number [up to 21] of general categories of difference between SAE and SBE, which I used to think were just much fewer than what I read in the course pack. However, I greatly appreciate that the SAE and SBE are variants of world English and, thus, more similar than different (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25).

What I found most exciting in reading the chapter is that I used to consider US English as adulterated English spoken by people who wish to show off. However, this thought has been clarified mainly through reading the study material. I changed my notion that each of the two English is spoken formally as the official national language for the respective countries.

Lastly, I was a bit confused in trying to differentiate between some examples given in the course pack to showcase the difference between the US and UK English. I copied and pasted directly from the course pack:

1. Dr. Smith (GB), Dr. Smith (U.S.).
2. (GB) He's in the hospital with a broken leg. (US) He's in the hospital with a broken leg. (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021 26 - 27). I have not seen any difference between these two examples above.

5) PLAGIARISM – A SERIOUS OFFENCE

What struck me when studying the section on plagiarism from the course pack is that not only an unacknowledged quotation of somebody's wordings or visuals is considered plagiarism but even paraphrasing his ideas without giving him the due credit (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34). This aspect widens my horizon in understanding plagiarism's broad concept.

I appreciate the threshold of 18% as the maximum acceptable percentage for plagiarism at EUDLID university. I admit that I did not know this rule before starting this course. My earlier thought on plagiarism in the field of academics is that there is zero

tolerance for plagiarism across-the-board without acceptance of even a 1% level. After discussing with a PhD student at another university in Nigeria, he added to my knowledge that they accept a 20% maximum level in his university. All these are lovely learning that can guide my essay writing professionally.

Regarding the in-text citation done to avoid plagiarism, the course pack gives two different formats without explaining the recommended one. Page 2 displays an example of authors, year and page number (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 62), while page 35 gives another example of only authors and page numbers (Gerson and Gerson 143). These examples confused me about what format I should use. Although I finally resolved to use the first one being, the one that appears in several instances of EUCLID documents.

6) SELECTING THE RULE OF STYLE FOR THE ESSAY

The word 'consistent' is the most reoccurring keyword I noticed in selecting the rule of style from the course pack. Although EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), a writer should be consistent in using whatever writing style guide he chooses for his essay, with no unprofessional mix-up (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41). What I found very interesting regarding the rule of style is that it has so many aspects ranging from the preferred length of sentences, manuscript layout, and font usage to as many as more than 15 aspects that a writer has to understand to enable him to write well. It seems to be broader than punctuation and grammar and requires different angles to look at it.

One of the most significant learning points I appreciate concerning the rules of style is that before enrolling in this course, I did not know that there were many writing rules as I see them now. I thought the usual APA taught in Nigerian universities was the universally accepted style. I now understand that APA is just one of many styles out there. I also understand now that certain disciplines have their preferred rules. For example, health students should use the WHO style; legal students should use the Blue Book style and so on.

The course pack refers me to the BBC News Style Guide link, which I visited and found highly encouraging and relevant for any student offering ACA 401. Although the site is only a guide for the journalist, I learnt a lot from reading through its rule. It provides rules on the style of numbers, grammar, spelling, pronunciation, military, names, religion, etc. It systematically arranged the style alphabetically for easier browsing on any rule one wants to find out ("BBC News Style Guide" n.d.).

7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, reading the period one study material has given me much encouragement and the feeling that the remaining periods (periods 2-5) will guide me to be a good essay writer. I came across so many areas that I got clarified and had many of my questions answered. Although I still have some issues to refer to even after submitting

the period one response paper. But generally, the study material is designed professionally to guide students in whatever discipline they study.

REFERENCES

“BBC News Style Guide.” n.d. Accessed October 15, 2022.
<https://www.bbc.co.uk/bbc.com/newsstyleguide/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.